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A Study of Classroom Management Macro and Micro Functions of Code-Switching as Perceived by the Teachers and Students in Undergraduate Classes

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the perceptions of teachers and students regarding the macro and micro functions of code-switching in undergraduate classes at the university level. It explored the functions of code-switching among students and teachers for classroom management at the undergraduate level. It was conducted utilizing the quantitative method. The study population consisted of undergraduate students from both public and private universities in Lahore. Cluster sampling technique was used to collect data from 2 public and 2 private sector universities. Five Likert questionnaires were designed to collect data from 68 teachers and 435 students. The data was analyzed using SPSS. The research findings showed that students had a more positive opinion regarding the role of code-switching in facilitating classroom management as compared to the teachers. Both the students and teachers agreed that code-switching facilitated better classroom communication.

Key words: Code Switching, Code Mixing, Medium of Instruction, Classroom Management

1 Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

The use of two or more linguistic varieties in the same discourse or interaction is known as code-switching. It might be for a single word or several phrases. The variations might be between two completely different languages or two dialects of the same language. Code-switching occurs when two bilingual speakers are communicating with each other. It does not include the usage of single, established borrowed words or phrases from a different language. Code-switching (CS) has been investigated by sociolinguistics to learn why people who are bilingual, switch between languages in a discussion or a setting. The majority of the time, such people are completely unaware that they are part of a linguistic phenomenon. Code-switching can be used for self-expression and is a way of changing the language for the sake of attaining personal goals and intention.

In “bi/multilingual” settings, learning is increased when students are allowed the opportunity to develop their current language abilities in two or more languages rather than being limited to monolingual teaching premises and practices. They also learn more effectively (Hornberger, 2005). Bilingualism occurs when more than one language is used in the same conversation. Bilingualism is utilized by different tutors to promote flexibility in using languages to increase the efficiency of education in the classroom (García & Wei, 2014).

When we use two languages for study, it is called bilingual education. Bilingual education helps learners become more competent in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. There are two ways of implementing bilingual education: one-way or two-way. One-way bilingual education means knowing two different languages. It implies that the proficiency level is not high in one language. In this system, only one group learns bilingually. In the case of two-way bilingual education, students receive instructions in both languages. Some of them are native speakers of one language while others are native speakers of another language and the teachers switch the codes to educate them

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in a better way. There are countries where numerous languages are spoken, so the teachers often use multilingualism in the classrooms. A speaker's capability to speak multiple languages with some level of fluency is called multilingualism. In this scenario, the speaker can understand and speak multiple languages—this phenomenon is generally from both perspectives i.e., individual and societal (Cenoz, 2013).

Levine (2003) has claimed that if native language 1 (L1) is used correctly, it could be useful in learning to use the foreign language 2 (L2) in schools for vocabulary, grammar, and writing projects. Therefore, classroom code-switching could be a source of improved understanding and active class participation. Furthermore, students would feel more comfortable if they were provided help in the language they were more familiar with (Cahyani et al., 2016). Cook (2001) believed that allowing students to speak in their native language could help the students in mastering a second language and in facilitating their learning in class.

In the case of third world countries, a foreign language is also of great importance. English is used as a lingua franca at the national and international levels in educational institutions and professional fields. Almost 200 states around the globe are monolingual, yet the speakers speak 4000 to 5000 different languages. Various European countries check the success of educational programs related to achieving the goals of bilingualism. Due to the advancements in communication and globalization, English plays different roles in education. It is used as a lingua franca in most instances. However, multilingualism exists in the educational systems almost at every level, from schools to universities in both the public and private sectors. In Pakistan, there are three distinct educational systems: public Urdu-medium schools, private English-medium schools, and religious institutions or Madrassahs (Coleman, 2010; Rahman, 2004).

1.2 Research Objectives

The present study is confined to the following research objectives:

- To investigate the macro and micro functions of code-switching in the classroom.
- To explore teachers' and students' perceptions (beliefs, opinions, and attitudes) towards code-switching.
- To find out the difference between perceptions of classroom management.
- To find out the perceptions of Urdu and English medium students and teachers regarding the use of code switching in classroom settings.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the teachers' and students' perceptions regarding the macro and micro functions of code-switching?
 - a. What are the teachers' and students' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching for classroom management?
2. What are the Urdu and English medium teachers' and students' perceptions regarding code-switching functions for the classroom?

1.4 Significance of the Study

The study is significant in that it would help understand the attitude of the students and teachers towards code-switching and its significance for classroom management and effective communication. The study would also help to understand the communicative intentions of the teachers and students based on the process and functions of code-

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switching used. This study is significant because it would be helpful in the teacher training programs to give them acquaintance with which code-switching functions work more and are beneficial for the students in certain situations. This study could also be used for the curriculum development of ELT (English language teaching) programs. This study could also help future researchers look into other areas of research within this domain.

1.5 Statement of the Problem

In higher education in a bilingual society, both students and teachers may face certain problems related to content delivery, classroom management, and interpersonal relations when using certain features of code-switching in the classroom. These problems may be reduced or rectified with the proper use of code-switching. The present study focuses on identifying the perceptions of students and teachers regarding the effective use of code-switching facilities better in the classroom.

2. Literature Review

Bilingualism, the simultaneous use of two or more languages, is one of the most used methods for assisting and facilitating individuals in multilingual language settings (Gardner- Chloros, 2009, p.4). Moreover, bilingualism and multilingualism, according to Baker (2017), are defined as the use of two languages by a person or by a speech community, as the habitual language of a certain area or country.

Bloomfield (1933) & Bahtia (2021) stated that "Bilingualism and multilingualism is the ability of a natural speaker to control two languages." It is a fact that even a monolingual may manage different styles and levels of the language he speaks. If a speaker gains some knowledge and aptitude of a second language, he/she may gain proficiency in it which may ultimately lead to bilingualism and multilingualism as a result of their experience. Tehrim et al (2025) explores every individual has one prominent intelligence and it can be interpersonal or intrapersonal.

Grosjean (1982) & Moore (1995) stated bilingualism was acquiring two different competencies or developing a mixed repertoire, original and complex. Furthermore, various languages in contact interact and merge in the classroom discourse. The bilingualism phenomenon is also studied with reference to the learning process. L1 is both an embodiment of bilingualism and possibly assists in its development. This perspective takes to further choices in the roles allocated to L1 in the classroom at the macro-level (Gajo, 2000:112).

More precisely, the experience of teaching and learning is based on the language shift. The basic concept is that the alternating use of two languages strengthens the awareness of the relationship between things and their labels and increases one's ability to distinguish between words and ideas. Through the communicative usage of the two languages, the language change helps to promote metalinguistic awareness among speakers (Coste, 1994a; Coste & Pasquier, 1992; Gajo & Serra, 1999).

Sipra (2009) is of the view that bilingualism is an effective tool in a language classroom and L2 is a facilitator in the process of teaching/learning at any level or grade. In Pakistan, many students lack communicative competence in the English language which results in code-switching from English to Urdu, a common phenomenon seen in the language classrooms. Teachers also tended to switch from English to Urdu to make the students understand difficult concepts, for a better clarification or simply for socialization in the class. Teachers in Pakistani classrooms have been reported to switch

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to L1 to make their lessons easy and understandable for their students. (Gulzar, 2010). Zabrodska (2007) affirmed that bilingual speakers had more advantages as compared to monolinguals. For instance, bilingual teachers could effectively use two languages to teach the content.

According to Swain (1983), for successful bilingual education, it is necessary that children receive a strong grounding in their first language as it facilitates them in the development of their second language skills. Code-switching facilitates students to communicate simply and helps them in their learning process (Simon, 2001).

In multilingual societies, code-switching is an inevitable outcome of language contact (Muhammad & Mahmood, 2013; Rafi, 2013; Rasul, 2013). On the other hand, research has shown that using one's mother language while teaching a second language is no longer viewed as a negative phenomenon, but rather something that should be incorporated into the classroom (Cook, 2013; Timor, 2012).

Saddhono and Rohmadi stated that teachers understood the necessity to switch codes to help their students to better learn in class and to balance the students' linguistic abilities. Code-switching has also been used by teachers to reinforce terms and ideas while also introducing new concepts and new subjects to students (Chowdhury, 2012). Shahraki (2012) stated that the code-switching by teachers during classroom discussions was necessary to reduce the anxiety and nervousness of the frightened and hesitant students and learners with low self-esteem. CS facilitated students' comprehension of the material and helped create good teacher-student relationships (Moghadam & Samad, 2012).

3. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The present study is based on Ferguson's theoretical framework for the functions of classroom code-switching (Ferguson, 2009). Ferguson's categorization (2003) framework has been used to investigate the teachers' and students' perceptions about facilitating the role of macro and micro functions of code-switching for classroom management (CM).

3.2 Research design

The study is quantitative in nature and was conducted using the survey method. The data collection instrument was designed as a questionnaire consisting of the five Likert scales to measure the perceptions of teachers and students regarding the facilitating role of code-switching in classroom teaching and learning at the undergraduate level. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS. The study also explored the significance level of the attitudes of the teachers and students towards the different macro and micro functions of code-switching.

3.3 Sources of data

The study explains the extent to which the teachers and students code-switched in the classroom and their attitudes towards it. Both teachers and students were consulted. The following section describes this study's data collection procedure, the participants and how they were selected. The data was collected through a questionnaire.

3.4 Population and Sampling

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A cluster survey technique was employed in this study. The study population comprised the undergraduate students and teachers, from various disciplines, in both public and private sector universities in Pakistan. Cluster sampling technique was used in the present study. The sample consisted of 68 Teachers and 435 students from various private and public sector universities in Pakistan.

The private and public universities included the University of Management and Technology (UMT), the University of Lahore (UOL), the University of Education (UE) and the University of the Punjab (PU).

3.5 Data Collection Process and Tools

There were two survey questionnaires for conducting the data collection from the students and the teachers. In the questionnaires, the Likert scale with five choices for each item was employed (1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Not Sure, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree). The survey questionnaires consisted of 24 closed-ended questions to investigate the macro and micro functions of code-switching in the classroom. Each macro function had 8 statements. All questionnaire items were close-ended.

The questionnaires were based on agreement scale questions. The perceptions of teachers and students were measured to know their tendency regarding the macro and micro functions of code-switching in the classroom. The questionnaire consists of surety and confidence at first so that the participant would feel confident regarding their information and their views. The 24

questions were designed to note the views of the teachers and students regarding their attitudes and perceptions.

Demographic data collected included information regarding the sector, gender, medium of instruction, and native languages spoken.

Data collection was carried out between July to December 2021. The researcher herself collected data from various institutes in Lahore, Pakistan by presenting the questionnaire to the participants.

3.6 Data Analysis Method

For the data analysis, quantitative approach was used. For this purpose, the data analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The relevance of each question was counted by calculating the frequency percentages and applying an independent-sample t-test to explain the perception of students and teachers regarding the facilitating role of code-switching for classroom management, content transmission and interpersonal relations. A statistically significant value was considered as P-Value < 0.05. The results were demonstrated in a table. A relative statistical method was utilized to obtain the percentages of responses for each item related to the functions of the code-switching and the t-test was performed to determine the relationship between the independent parameters of a questionnaire.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data of the study were derived from the questionnaire survey administered to the chosen sample of students and teachers. There were 437 (86.5%) students and 68 (13.5%) teachers engaged in undergraduate education in public and private universities in Pakistan. Data were collected from the students and teachers from different disciplines. The responses were gathered from the survey and analyzed through SPSS. An independent sample t-test was also applied.

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The questionnaires comprised three sections with a total of 24 structured closed-ended questions that were developed to measure the various functions of the classroom. It also included questions to obtain a background of the participants by asking for their demographic details. The three sections of the questionnaire were regarding 1 macro function of Classroom Management (CM) and this section included eight items.

4.1 Macro and Micro Functions of Code-Switching as perceived by the Teachers and Students for Classroom Management (CM), Content Transmission (CT) and Interpersonal Relations (IR)

Table 4.1

Table 4.1 presents data about the demographic variables with sample distributions. It can be seen that the data was collected from 21 male and 12 female teachers, and 116 male and 98 female students. Notably, there were 18 male and 17 female teachers, and 135 male and 88 female students from private sector universities.

Table 4.1: Distribution of Sample according to Demographics Variables

Respondents	Public		Private		Totals
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Teachers	21	12	18	17	68
Students	114	98	135	88	435
Sub Totals	135	110	153	105	503
Totals	245		258		
<i>Students and Teachers Frequency %</i>					
Disciplines	Social Sciences and Humanities		204		40.4
	Natural Sciences		141		27.9
	Engineering and Technology		93		18.4
	Total Students		435		86.7
	Total Teachers		67		13.3
	Total		503		100.0

Table 4.2

The following table indicates the perception of teachers and students regarding the facilitating role of code switch for classroom management.

Table 4.2: Independent Sample t-Test on the students' and teachers' opinions regarding the use of Code-Switching for Classroom Management (CM)

Sr.	CM item	Mean	Df		P-Value
			Students	Teachers Difference	
1	CS helps during giving instruction.	3.90	3.79	.11	503.349

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2	CS helps to negotiate direction in classroom.	3.77	3.66	.11	503.307
3	CS is effective in answering questions.	4.01	3.72	.29*	503.007
4	CS develops effective learning in the classroom.	3.83	3.73	0.1	503.432
5	CS helps to focus on tasks or assignment.	3.85	3.83	.02	503.899
6	CS assists to get student's response.	3.81	3.86	.05	503.582
7	CS facilitates to get students attention.	4.02	3.00	1.02*	503.004
8	CS helps to manage discipline in classroom.	3.01	3.50	.49*	503.001
Total score of CM		3.78	3.52	1.118*	5030.018

The table indicates that there was a significant difference (level of difference is 0.05) between the students' perceptions (M= 3.78) and the teachers' perceptions (M =3.52) regarding the 8 micro functions of code-switching for "Classroom Management".

There was a statistically significant difference between the opinion of students and teachers about the facilitating role of code-switching in answering questions (Student M=4.01, Teacher M= 3.72), getting students' attention (Student M= 4.02, Teacher M= 3.00), and managing the discipline in the classroom (Student M=3.01, Teacher M= 3.50).

Among the micro functions, the teachers' highest preference was for getting students' responses (Teacher M=3.86) and the lowest preference was for getting students' attention in the class (Teacher M=3.00). To this effect, students' highest preference was for getting students' attention (Student M=4.02) and the lowest preference was for managing discipline in the classroom (Student M=3.01).

Medium of Instruction (MOI) Table 4.3

The table below indicates the t-test value of Urdu and English medium students' perception regarding which medium of instruction facilitates them in the classroom management functions. Teachers used whichever medium (Urdu and English) was identified for better learning in the classroom and helps students to understand the classroom problems.

Table 4.3: Independent Sample t-Test of Urdu and English Medium Students' Perceptions on role of Code-Switching in Classroom Management (CM)

Sr. CM item	Mean			Df	P-Value
	Urdu Students	English Students	Difference		
1 CS helps during giving instruction.	3.92	3.88	.04	435	0.630
2 CS helps to negotiate direction in classroom.	3.75	3.79	.04	435	0.606
3 CS is effective in answering questions.	4.03	4.00	.03	435	0.651

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4	CS develops effective learning in the classroom.	3.92	3.73	.19*	4350.040	
5	CS helps to focus on tasks or assignment.	3.85	3.85	0	4350.983	
6	CS assists to get student's response.	3.80	3.81	.01	4350.966	
7	CS facilitates to get students attention.	4.21	3.85	.36	4350.204	
8	CS helps to manage discipline in classroom.	3.03	3.00	.03	4350.073	
	Total score of CM		3.81	3.74	0.6	4350.094

The Table indicates that there was no significant difference (level of difference of 0.05) between Urdu medium students' perceptions (M= 3.81) and English medium students' perceptions (M =3.74) regarding the 8 micro functions of code-switching for "Classroom Management".

The data shows that there was a statistically significant difference between Urdu and English medium students' perceptions about the facilitation role of CS for developing effective learning in the classroom (Urdu Medium Student M= 3.92, English Medium Student M= 3.73).

Regarding the micro functions of classroom management, Urdu medium students' highest preference was for CS facilitation in getting students' attention in the class (Urdu Medium Student M=4.21) and the lowest preference was for managing discipline in the classroom (Urdu Medium Student M= 3.03). To this effect, English medium Students' highest preference was for CS facilitation in answering questions (English Medium Student M=4.00) and the lowest preference was for managing discipline in the classroom (English Medium Student M= 3.00).

Table 4.4

Table 4.4 reveals the t-test value of teacher perception regarding the role of code-switching of Urdu and English as a medium of instruction for classroom management.

Table 4.4: Independent Sample t-Test of Urdu and English Medium Teachers' Perceptions regarding Code-Switching for Classroom Management (CM)

Sr. CM item	Mean		DfP-Difference	Value
	Urdu Teachers	English Teachers		
1 CS helps during giving instruction.	3.81	3.77	.04	680.820
2 CS helps to negotiate direction in classroom.	3.93	3.40	.53*	680.007
3 CS is effective in answering questions.	3.93	3.51	.42*	680.012
4 CS develops effective learning in the classroom.	3.81	3.65	.16	680.423
5 CS helps to focus on tasks or assignment.	3.90	3.77	.13	680.424
6 CS assists to get student's response.	3.87	3.85	.02	680.913

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7	CS facilitates to get students attention.	2.93	3.05	.12	68 0.599
8	CS helps to manage discipline in classroom.	3.51	3.48	.03	68 0.911
	Total score of CM	3.71	3.56	1.24	68 0.070

The table indicates that there was no significant difference (0.05 level of difference) between the Urdu medium teachers' perceptions (M= 3.71) and English medium teachers' perceptions (M =3.56) regarding the 8 micro functions of code switching for "Classroom Management".

There was a statistically significant difference between Urdu and English medium teachers' perceptions about the facilitating role of CS for negotiating directions in the class (Urdu Medium Teacher M=3.93, English Medium Teacher M= 3.40) and for answering questions (Urdu Medium Teacher M=3.93, English Medium Teacher M=3.51).

Among the micro functions of classroom management, Urdu medium teachers' highest preference was for CS facilitation in negotiating directions in the class (Urdu Medium Teacher M=3.93) and the lowest preference was for getting the students' attention (Urdu Medium Teacher M= 2.93). To this effect, English medium teachers' highest preference was for getting the students' response (English Medium Teacher M=3.85 and the lowest preference was for attaining the students' attention (English Medium Teacher M=3.05).

Table 4.5

The below table shows the overall independent sample t-test value of the Urdu and English medium students and their perception regarding which medium of instruction helped them in CM, CT and IR functions. Teachers and students used which medium of instruction (Urdu and English) for classroom learning.

Table 4.5: Independent Sample t-Test for MOI of the Urdu and English Students' and Teachers' perceptions regarding Macro and Micro Functions of code-switching

	Mean				
MOI	Grand Total	Urdu	English	Difference	df P Value
Students	3.76	3.75	1.3*	435	0.033
Teachers	3.84	3.72	2.82	68	0.141

Table 4.5 indicates that there was a significant difference (0.05 level) between the Urdu medium Students' perceptions (Urdu Medium Student M=3.76) and the English medium students' perceptions (English Medium Student M =3.75) regarding the macro and micro functions of code-switching for "Classroom Management, Content Transmission and Interpersonal Relations". However, there was no statistically significant difference (0.05 level of difference) found between the Urdu medium teachers' perceptions (Urdu Medium Teacher M=3.84) and the English medium teachers' perceptions (English Medium Teacher M =3.72) regarding the macro and micro functions of code-switching for "Classroom Management, Content Transmission and Interpersonal Relations".

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In the findings of the questionnaires administered to the students and the teachers, it was noted that both the teachers and the students switched codes from English to Urdu to perform various functions in different language teaching classes. The majority of the students used code-switching to accomplish the class tasks, for answering questions, explaining ideas, building arguments, reinforcing key points, achieving communicative competence, comprehending the class objectives, reducing anxiety levels and getting class attention. The teachers, on the other hand, used code-switching to assist them in switching topics, reinforcing basic concepts, checking the understanding of learners, managing their classes, facilitating their expressions, and increasing the classroom participation to better serve their students. Consequently, the usage of code-switching facilitated the students to understand the classroom learning environment, improve class communications and develop their interest in the class related subject content.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the teachers' and students' perceptions regarding macro and micro functions of code-switching in undergraduate classes at the university level. Data from this study was collected through a questionnaire. There are 503 participants in this survey including teachers and students from different disciplines. The questionnaires consisted of demographic pieces of information of participants and covered one parameters of CS (Classroom Management).

The first objective of this study was to investigate the macro and micro functions of code-switching. The second objective was to explore the teachers' and students' perceptions (beliefs, opinions, and attitudes) towards code-switching. The third objective covered the difference between perceptions of teachers and students regarding classroom management. Fourth and the last objective was to find out the teachers' and students' medium of instruction in the classroom.

The overall data revealed that the teachers and students considered code-switching to be an effective strategy for CM. But the ratio of the students was greater than teachers. They considered that code-switching helped them in classroom participation and facilitated them in class agendas. The Urdu medium teachers and students agreed more on the positive role of code-switching in classroom management rather than the English medium students and teachers. In this way, code-switching was found to help enable congenial learning. This research concentrated on both the students' and teachers' perceptions regarding classroom functions to understand the efficacy of code-switching in the classroom.

6. Ethical considerations

This present study was collected material based and had ethical considerations as presented by Wray and Bloomer (2006:173-176). All participants were informed about the study and its general purpose. They were also informed that their participation was voluntary. The information was conveyed in English to ensure that the participants understood each statement. The teachers' and students' involvement was kept confidential and contact details were only maintained so that future contact was possible if needed (Wray & Bloomer, 2006:174). The respondents to the questionnaire were guaranteed anonymity.

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